

PARIS-EST CRÉTEIL UNIVERSITY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The French Higher Education system is composed of 74 public universities, but there are also engineering schools and RPOs that do not deliver diplomas but often help train doctoral students – such as the National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS). There are also 13 private universities recognised by the state. The gender policy implemented at universities and RPOs is set by the French Ministry of Education, Research, and Innovation (MESRI). This policy has focused on gender-based violence (GBV) since about 2015, whereas previous policies focused more on careers. Today, while equality is still an objective, GBV has become a central issue. The Conference of University Presidents has also been active on this issue for at least 10 years¹ and drew up the first charter in 2013.² In 2019, all universities and RPOs were required to set up help units³ that would be in charge of fighting sexual and sexist violence, training, and communication (more than 90% of the universities now have one). The ministry supports these actions financially through an annual call for proposals, which took place in 2021 and 2022. In 2020 a decree to support the reporting of harassment and violence was issued that applies to the entire civil service (therefore including public universities and RPOs).⁴ The MESRI published a guide on the reporting procedures in effect in 2020,⁵ and a general reference document on mandatory equality action plans that include GBV.⁶ No university has been sanctioned for not complying with the regulations so far, but the issue will be on the table when they undergo their evaluations every 5 years.

¹ <http://www.cpu.fr/actualite/lutte-contre-les-violences-sexuelles-et-sexistes-des-outils-a-disposition-des-etablissements/>

² http://www.cpu.fr/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/chartes_dossier_couv_239902.pdf

³ Act No. 2019-828 of 6 August 2019 on transforming the civil service.

⁴ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000041722970/>

⁵ https://cache.media.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/file/Parite_et_lutte_contre_les_discriminations/06/7/vss_enquete_guide_esri_03n_1353067.pdf

⁶ http://www.cdefi.fr/files/files/20201000 - Referentiel_plan_d_action_egalite_dans_l_ESR.pdf

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

International Space University (ISU) is a private non-profit structure founded in 1987, that used to be based at MIT in the United State but was moved to Strasburg around 1995. Its public is essentially the international space community and those who wish to join it. It organises an intensive 9-week training in various places around the world. A Master was also created in 1995. It was formally recognised as an institute of higher education by the French Ministry of Education in 2004.

ISU has two main policy documents: an Academic Handbook, which contains a Code of Conduct and Ethics that the students have to sign, and an Anti-Harassment Policy. Both documents are broader documents that are not specifically dedicated to gender-based violence (GBV).

URLs

- › Academic Handbook: <https://www.isunet.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/ISU-Academic-Handbook-V4.0-FINAL-2020.11.06.pdf>
- › Anti-Harassment Policy: <https://www.isunet.edu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/ISU-Anti-Harassment-Policy-July-2020.pdf>
- › Amendment to the Anti-Harassment Policy: https://www.isunet.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/ISU-AHP-Amendment_1-9_17-Dec-21.pdf

Entry into force: the Academic Handbook entered into force in 2020 and the Anti-Harassment Policy in 2019, with an amendment in force as of 2021.

TRAINING

There are no GBV training activities.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

None. There is no research conducted on these issues.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined address the following **eight** forms of violence: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, stalking, organisational violence, and online violence. The Anti-Harassment Policy addresses more forms of GBV than the Academic Handbook. The latter focuses on physical violence, sexual violence, and sexual and gender-based harassment, while the Anti-Harassment Policy does not address physical violence but adds psychological violence, stalking, organisational violence, and online violence.

Gender-Based Violence

Physical Violence

Psychological Violence

Sexual Violence

Sexual Harassment

Gender-Based Harassment

Economic and Financial Violence

Stalking

Organisational Violence

Online Violence

Other

7Ps covered: Both policies address the same **4Ps** – protection, prosecution, provision of services and policies.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: The two policies combined address all target groups, **academic staff, non-academic staff, and students**. The Anti-Harassment Policy also identifies other groups as anyone involved in ISU programmes as well as visitors.

The Anti-Harassment Policy identifies the following **seven** groups as vulnerable to GBV: students with disabilities, staff and students from migrant and/or ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ staff and students, new and expectant mothers, as well as other groups, such as persons with specific political affiliations and language or socioeconomic status. The Academic Handbook does not identify any vulnerable group.

Intersectionality addressed

No.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. Both policies address bystanders. The Academic Handbook states that students, staff, and faculty who witness violations of the ISU Code of Conduct and Ethics are encouraged to approach the offender in a manner that can lead to informal resolution of the offence. Every attempt should be made to resolve the situation in a manner that assists the offender to correct his/her behaviour while maintaining the integrity of ISU and other individuals who may be involved.

The Anti-Harassment Policy describes the role of bystanders as follows: "Any employee or other person involved in an ISU program (Section 2) who believes they have been harassed or who has witnessed harassment of another, must immediately report the facts of the incident or incidents and the names of the individuals involved."

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. Only the Academic Handbook addresses the aspect, see the paragraph on bystanders above.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Academic Handbook and the Code of Conduct and Ethics set out a **single step-by-step procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and sanctions.

Who to contact: When a student is involved in an offence, the person to contact is the director of the relevant ISU programme; when it is a member of the ISU faculty, it is the dean; in other cases, it is the ISU president.

How to report: A complaint is made in writing and the responsible persons must provide a copy of the written complaint to the individual against whom the complaint has been made as soon as is feasible but no later than two weeks after the complaint has been lodged. Whenever possible and appropriate, informal resolution and mediation shall be applied to resolve issues of individual behaviour before resorting to formal disciplinary procedures.

Responsible persons/units: To investigate a case of misconduct, the president of the ISU appoints a Committee on Academic Conduct and Ethics (CACE). The CACE is composed of: the director of personnel, a representative of the Central Campus faculty, elected by the resident faculty members and appointed by the president; a representative of the staff who is not a Central Campus faculty member, elected by the staff and appointed by the president; or, when the case involves a faculty member, another Central Campus faculty member elected by the resident faculty members and appointed by the president; the dean, if the case involves an academic staff member; and the president who chairs the committee. During a Space Studies Programme (SSP), the president of ISU delegates to the SSP Director the duty to appoint an SSP Committee on Academics, Conduct, and Ethics (SSP/CACE).

Outcomes: The CACE determines if the accusations are valid and then issues the results of the investigation. A one-page summary of the outcome of all investigations shall be copied to the ISU Academic Unit to be kept on file.

Sanctions: No reference is made to legal sanctions. Disciplinary sanctions include a notice of probation or the expulsion of the perpetrator. A written warning or notice of probation must explicitly state that further disciplinary action will ensue if the individual fails to achieve a satisfactory level of behaviour within the defined probationary period. During the time of this warning or probationary period the individual's behaviour shall be closely monitored in an effort to effect improvement or change.

The written warning or notice of probation will include:

- a) the date of the probationary period;
- b) the specific nature of the problem(s) resulting in the probation;
- c) the corrective action required, including specific and reasonable standards related to the deficiencies outlined in item b, above; and
- d) the consequences of failure.

If new significant problems of behaviour arise during the probationary period, the individual on probation may be immediately dismissed, or they may be suspended from registration in an ISU programme for a specified period, or a recommendation may be made that the individual be expelled from ISU. A letter of suspension or termination will be issued that will be effective on the date of the decision.

No member of the ISU staff or the ISU College of Teachers, whether resident at the Central Campus or in residence at the host site during an SSP or Southern Hemisphere Space Study Programme (SHSPP), should be subject to disciplinary actions, including dismissal, unless there is a just and sufficient cause that can be demonstrated before an independent third-party hearing of peers and/or before an impartial body. Equitable safeguards are established at each stage of any disciplinary procedure, including dismissal, as explained below.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Suzanne de Cheveigné in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

